

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL FOR:

Positive regulation of *DLT* operon by *TCSR7* enhances acid resistance of *Lactococcus lactis* F44

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Table S1 List of strains and plasmids used in this study.

Names	Descriptions	Sources
Strains		
<i>Lactococcus lactis subsp. lactis</i> F44	<i>L. lactis</i> subsp. <i>lactis</i> F44 (Accession number: PRJNA419050)	Laboratory stock (Zhang et al., 2014)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> TG1	Plasmid preparation	Laboratory stock
<i>Escherichia coli</i> BL21(DE3)	Protein expression	Laboratory stock
Plasmids		
pLEB124	Expression vector; Em ^r	Laboratory stock
pLEB124- <i>DLTD</i>	DLTD expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>ERFK</i>	ERFK expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>DACB</i>	DACB expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>HRTA</i>	HRTA expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>YLBA</i>	YLBA expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>YIDC</i>	YIDC expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>DACA</i>	DACA expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>0883</i>	0883 expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>1610</i>	1610 expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>TCSR7</i>	TCSR7 expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pLEB124- <i>RCFB</i>	RCFB expression vector; Em ^r	This study
pET28A	Protein expression; Kan ^r	Laboratory stock
pET28A- <i>TCSR7</i>	TCSR7 expression; Kan ^r	This study
pET28A- <i>RCFB</i>	RCFB expression; Kan ^r	This study

Table S2 List of primers used for RT-qPCR in this study.

Names	Sequence (5' to 3')	Region in F44 genome	Length
Q1-DLTD-F	TGCCACAGAGTTCATGTAGA	1323656..1323764	109bp
Q1-DLTD-R	TCACCCAAGTGCCTATTTCA		
Q1-ERFK-F	TACCTACTGGAAGAGACCCC	2337211..2337311	101bp
Q1-ERFK-R	GCTAGGGAAATCTCCTGCAT		
Q1-DACB-F	ACCTGACGCTAAACAATCAGA	1002209..1002335	127bp
Q1-DACB-R	AACCGCTGATGCTATCCTTT		
Q1-HRTA-F	TTGGATTAATGGCCGAGCTT	2415299..2415411	113bp
Q1-HRTA-R	CCGTTAAGAATGGCACGAGA		
Q1-YLBA-F	TTACCTACCGACGTTATGCC	1094103..1094247	145bp
Q1-YLBA-R	AAACCGACACTTTTCAGCAC		
Q1-yidC-F	GATTGTTATTCGGGCAGCAT	100991..101103	113bp
Q1-yidC-R	TGCTTGGGTATTTAGCCTGA		
Q1-0883-F	GGAACGAGATACGATGACGA	957027..957151	125bp
Q1-0883-R	TGGCATAAGTGACAGCAGAT		
Q1-1610-F	GCCAGTAGTTGTATTACCGC	1795955..1796036	82bp
Q1-1610-R	GAATCCAGAAGCTGAAGCAC		
Q1-DACA-F	TCAACTCCTTTCCTCTCACAA	2423150..2423281	132bp
Q1-DACA-R	TTTTCTTTTCCATCAATCACA		
Q1-16S-F	TCAAATCATCATGCCCTTAT	2430051..2430374	324bp
Q1-16S-R	CCGATACGGCTACCTTGTTAC		
Q2-DACA-F	TCTGGTGCTTCAGCAACAA	2422832..2422975	144bp
Q2-DACA-R	GGTCATCTTTGCTTCATTGC		

Q2-DLTD-F	AAACCACTGACCGCTCTACA		
		1323305..1323418	114bp
Q2-DLTD-R	AAGTCCAAGAGGTTGTGCTG		
Q2-ERFK-F	TTATTCTTCGGCAGGCGT		
		2337399..2337509	111bp
Q2-ERFK-R	GCATAGTTTGCTCCCTCCC		
Q2-TCSR7-F	TGGGCTACCATTTTATAGTGG		
		1852180..1852301	122bp
Q2-TCSR7-R	CTTGATTCATAGCGGTTACTTG		
Q2-RCFB-F	ATTGGGTACGCGAAGATTT		
		2384407..2384542	132bp
Q2-RCFB-R	CTATGGAGACAAGCACAAACTG		

Table S3 List of primers used for construction of plasmids in this study.

Names	Sequence (5' to 3')	Region in F44 genome	Length
DACB-F	CGCGGATCCGAGAAATAGGGAGTGAAAAGTTAGC	1002017.	784bp
DACB-R	TCCCCCGGGTTTCCTTTATGCTGGTAATAGTTTT	.1002800	
DLTD-F	CGCGGATCCGTTTCAGGAAAAAAGGATGAA	1322720.	1303bp
DLTD-R	TCCCCCGGGTTAATTTACTATAGACTCTGTTGCAC	.1324022	
ERFK-F	CGCGGATCCGATGTGTTTCCAGTCACTAAAATC	2337167.	680bp
ERFK-R	TCCCCCGGGTAAACTCGACTTCTTTTTTT	.2337846	
YLBA-F	CGCGGATCCGATGACATTTATTGAAGTGATTAATGA	1093846.	712bp
YLBA-R	TCCCCCGGGTCGCATAGCTTACCACTCAAT	.1094575	
YIDC-F	CGCGGATCCGAATCTATGTGGATGGAGAAAAC	100782..	900bp
YIDC-R	TCCCCCGGGGATAAAGCCTATTGACAATTTCTA	101681	
HRTA-F	CGCGGATCCGAAAAGCGATTGGATAGGAG	2415084.	714bp
HRTA-R	TCCCCCGGGAATACGAAGACTTCAAACCTTAGTC	.2415797	
0883-F	CGCGGATCCGATGAAAAGAAAAGAAATTAGACAA	956698..	1299bp
0883-R	TCCCCCGGGTTAATTAGCGGCTAAAGCTC	957996	
1610-F	CGCGGATCCGATTAATATGATTCCACATAGGAGA	1795874.	1194bp
1610-R	TCCCCCGGGTTCATTCTGTGATTGCCCT	.1797067	
DACA-F	CGCGGATCCGACGAATAGACTATGGTATAATCGAG	2422250.	1377bp
DACA-R	TCCCCCGGGTTTATAAGCTAATTTACTTACAGCTTT	.2423626	
RCFB-F	CGCGGATCCGACAGCCTTATATAGGCGAATAA	2384136.	789bp
RCFB-R	TCCCCCGGGATCATGCTGACCTAATTATAACAA	.2384924	
TCSR7-F	CGCGGATCCGAGTGAGTGATACAGAAATGATAGCA	1851737.	772bp
TCSR7-R	TCCCCCGGGGACATAAGCAAAAAGACACCAAT	.1852508	

E-RCFB-F	CATG <u>CCATGG</u> GCATGAGTTTTAATAAGATGGAAGAA	2384199.	684bp
E-RCFB-R	CCGCTCGAGACTAATATATTCTTCCAAATATTGAG	.2384822	
E-TCSR7-F	CATG <u>CCATGG</u> GCATGACTAAAATATTTATTGTAGAAG ATGA	1851788.	669bp
E-TCSR7-R	CCGCTCGAGAACCAGAGCATAACCACTTCC	.1852456	

¹Underlined letters indicate restriction sites.

Table S4 List of primers used for DNA pull-down in this study.

Names	Sequence (5' to 3')	Region in F44 genome	length
b-DACB-F	ATTGCTCGTGGCGGTC	1000659..1000898	240bp
b-DACB-R	ATTAGCTCGTAAACCTGCTAAA		
b-DLTD-F	TGTTGTACCCTTAAAAATACAACA	1327061..1327339	279bp
b-DLTD-R	ATGACTGTAGGAATAAAGATAGAGC		
b-ERFK-F	TTAATTCACACCATAAATCAGCA	2337663..2337883	221bp
b-ERFK-R	GGAGTTGTATTTTCCTTTTTAGC		

Table S5 List of primers used for EMSA in this study.

Names	Sequence (5' to 3')	Region in F44 genome	Length
E-DACB-F	AGCCAGTGGCGATAAGATTGCTCGTGGCGGTC	1000659..1	240bp
E-DACB-R	AGCCAGTGGCGATAAGATTAGCTCGTAAACCTGCTAA AA	000898	
E-DLTD-F	AGCCAGTGGCGATAAGTGTTGTACCCTTAAAAATAC AACA	1327061..1	279bp
E-DLTD-R	AGCCAGTGGCGATAAGATGACTGTAGGAATAAAGAT AGAGC	327339	
E-ERFK-F	AGCCAGTGGCGATAAGTTAATTCACACCATAAATCAG CA	2337663..2	221bp
E-ERFK-R	AGCCAGTGGCGATAAGGGAGTTGTATTTTCCTTTTAA GC	337883	

¹AGCCAGTGGCGATAAG is a 16 bp homology arm.

Figure S1 The plasmid profile of pLEB124 recombinant plasmid for 9 genes.

¹The number of copies of the plasmid is 3-5.

Figure S2 Plasmid profiles of pET28A-TCSR7 and pET28A-RCFB.

